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OMBUDSMAN ZA PRAVA DETETA

Pored ombudsmana opšteg tipa, koji kontroliše sve grane uprave, postoje i specijalizovani ombudsmani, nadležni za kontrolu pojedinih upravnih oblasti, odnosno zaštitu određenih kategorija lica. Jedan od takvih specijalizovanih ombudsmana je ombudsman za zaštitu prava deteta. Prva zemlja koja je uvela ombudsmana ovakvog tipa je Kraljevina Norveška i to je učinjeno 1981. godine. Ombudsman za prava deteta u državama koje su ga uvele, nadležan je da štiti, prati i promoviše prava i interese dece na osnovu ustavnih i zakonskih normi, kao i međunarodnih ugovora. U radu, pored kraćeg uporedno-pravnog prikaza, analizira se položaj ovog ombudsmana u Republici Hrvatskoj i Republici Srpskoj. U Srbiji ovakav ombudsman ne postoji. U zaključnim razmatranjima, autor postavlja pitanje da li bi bilo dobro rešenje da u Republici Srbiji bude uveden ombudsman za prava deteta, kao vrsta specijalizovanog ombudsmana.

Ključne reči: ombudsman, prava deteta, specijalizovani ombudsmani, ombudsman za prava deteta.

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OMBUDSMAN FOR THE CHILDREN'S RIGHTS PROTECTION

In addition to the general ombudsman, who controls all branches of the public administration, there are also specialized ombudsmen, responsible for controlling certain administrative areas or the protection of certain categories of persons. One of such specialized ombudsmen is the Ombudsman for the Protection of Children's Rights. The first country to introduce this type of an ombudsman was the Kingdom of Norway, back in 1981. In the countries that introduced this institution, the Ombudsman for Children's Rights Protection is responsible for protecting, monitoring and promoting the rights and interests of children on the basis of constitutional and legal norms, as well as international treaties. In addition to a brief comparative law overview, the paper analyzes the position of this ombudsman in the Republic of Croatia and in Republika Srpska. This type of an ombudsman does not exist in Serbia. In the concluding remarks, the author discusses whether it would be a good solution to introduce as this type of specialized ombudsman for children's rights in the Republic of Serbia.

Keywords: ombudsman, children's rights, specialized ombudsmen, ombudsman for children's rights protection.